

Consumer Behaviour of Online Shopping with Special Reference towards Krishnagiri District

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Gunasekaran, N & Ramya, A. "Consumer Behaviour of Online Shopping with Special Reference towards Krishnagiri District." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 126–132.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1461458>

Dr.N.Gunasekaran

Principal, Morappur Kongu College of Arts and Science, Morappur

Mrs.A.Ramya

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, ERK Arts & Science College Erumiyampatti, Kokkarapatti (PO), Pappireddipatti (TK), Dharmapuri (DT)

Abstract

Online shopping plays great importance in the modern business environment. Online shopping has opened the door of opportunity and advantage to the firms. This paper analyzed the different issue of online shopping. Online shopping involves no travel, product carrying or restriction on online shopping hours, offering easy accessibility, convenience and time-saving.

This paper also identifies the problem faced by consumers when they want to accept internet online shopping. Like the impossibility of product testing, problems with complaints, product return and misuse of personal data are the main uncertainties regarding online shopping. The study provides insights into consumers online shopping behaviors and preferences. Findings reveals that online shopping brings optimum convenience to the consumers.

Keywords: Online shopping, Online buying behavior, Internet shopping, Buying motives, Online security.

Introduction

The project entitled Online Shopping enables the customer to buy mobiles or accessories from anywhere through online. This application advertises some of the products for shopping. To buy products, the customer has to create an account. Those who do not have an account, they can only view the available product. They can't buy it. Once the customer has created the account, not only he can view the products, he can also add the product to the cart and also he can place an order to buy those products. This application then generates the bill for that particular customer. After the confirmation, the customer has to enter his credit card details to buy those products.

Online shopping is a form of electronic shopping store where the buyer is directly online to the seller's computer usually via the internet. There is no intermediary service. The sale and purchase transaction is completed electronically and interactively in real-time. The development of this new system contains the following activities, which try to develop the on-line application by keeping the entire process in the view of the database integration approach. The

user gets its e mail id and password to access their account. Administrator of the shopping system has multiple features such as Add, Delete, Update shopping Items.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the consumer attitude towards online shopping. (Especially in case of Flip -kart, Amazon, etc.)
2. To identify the respondent's perception of online shopping.
3. To understand the consumer satisfaction level of online purchase.
4. To understand the factors influence consumers to online shopping.

The Scope of the Study

- The survey consisted of 100 samples.
- This study refers to all the categories of consumers.
- This study has been in all area of this district.
- This study provides a base for understanding the consumer's problems and brings out solutions to it.

Review of Literature

Yaobin. L (2013) "Influence of online users" online shopping causes enjoyment which is fun and playful rather than from shopping task completion; customers may regard the purchase of goods in online shopping as an experience and the perceived entertainment will be regarded as enjoyment to them.

Dong. M (2013) "Result of online shopping" Resulted that Hungarian shoppers visited shopping centers for both utilitarian and experiential reasons some viewed shopping as a leisure activity accompanied by somebody and enjoyed looking around while accomplishing their shopping task.

Isabel. P (2014) "Online store" Examined the role of several consumers cognitive and psychographic traits in their perceptions of retailer's practices and the different effects on perceived associated with online store shopping.

Methodology

The nature of the study is descriptive research. Types of data collected from the study have been utilized by primary data and secondary data.

Research Design

The researcher makes a plan for his study before the undertakes his research work. This will enable the researcher to save time and resources such a plan study or blueprint for the study is called Research design. In this descriptive type of research design has been used.

Data Collection

To achieve the objective of the study the data will be collected from both primary and secondary sources. The search of knowledge through the objective and systematic method of finding the solution to a problem is called research methodology thus refers to the method the research is in performing research operation. Research methodology is systematically solve the research problem.

Primary Data

The primary data will be collected by a certified random sampling method with the help of an interview schedules the necessary, field work shall be carried out. It means the data being collected

or obtained from firsthand experience. The present study collected the primary data through the direct interview, questionnaire, Observations.

Secondary Data

It means the data gathered in the past or obtained from another party. In this study secondary data collected through journals, report of online shopping, websites, etc., The study is based on both primary and secondary data.

What is Online Shopping?

Online shopping is the process of buying goods and services from merchants over the Internet. Since the emergence of the World Wide Web, merchants have sought to sell their products to people who spend time online. Shoppers can visit web stores from the comfort of their homes and shop as they sit in front of the computer.

Consumers can buy a huge variety of items from online stores, and just about anything can be purchased from companies that provide their products online. Books, clothing, household appliances, toys, hardware, software, and health insurance are just some of the hundreds of products consumers can buy from an online store. Many people choose to shop online because of the convenience.

Consumer's Attitudes toward Online Shopping

Consumer's attitudes toward online shopping have gained a great deal of attention in the empirical literature. Consistent with the literature and models of attitude change and behavior it is believed that consumer attitudes will affect intention to shop online and eventually whether a transaction is made. This is a multidimensional construct that has been conceptualized in several different ways in the existing literature. First, it refers to the consumer's acceptance of the Internet as a shopping channel. Secondly, it refers to consumer attitudes toward a specific Internet store.

Factors Influencing the Consumer to Online Shopping

Though there are several factors that influence consumers to shop online, as mentioned above researchers have selected four factors after reading literature in the field on consumer attitudes towards online shopping and these factors are discussed below in the light of previous literature.

- Convenience
- Time-saving
- Website design or features
- Security

Online Payment Methods

Making purchases through the Internet is a fact today and is successful. And one of the best gears that the Web offers today is the capability to take your business wherever on the planet through a website. This is why it became essential to purchase via the Internet through many payment service provider. Payment Service Provider is a company that provides online marketing services; it accepts payments electronically by managing transactions between seller and buyer. The most common payment methods that are usually offered are by credit card, bank transfer and real-time orders. All online payment systems are assigned a tax rate on transactions, fixed or variable.

Table Calculation

Table 1 Age

S. No	Age	No. of. Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative (%)
1	Bellow 20	32	32	32
2	21-30	50	50	82
3	31-40	14	14	96
4	Above 40	4	4	100
	Total	100	100	

Chart 1 Age

Interpretation

The above chart shows that age group of respondents among the 100 respondents, below 20 years respondents are 32% and 21-30 years respondents are 50% and 31-40 years respondents are 14% and remaining 4% respondents belong to above 40 years. The age between 21-30 respondents is the maximum customer in the online purchase.

Table 2 Income

S. No	Income	No. of. Respon- dents	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
1	Less than 10000	40	40	40
2	10000 – 20000	20	20	60
3	20000 – 30000	28	28	88
4	Above 30000	12	12	100
	Total	100	100	

Chart 2 Income

Interpretation

The above chart shows that 40% of respondents are less than Rs.10000, 20% of the respondents are 10000 – 20000, 28% of the respondents are 20000 – 30000 and 12% of the respondents are above 30000.

Table 4 Satisfaction Level of Online Shopping

S. No	Opinions	No. of. Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative (%)
1	Yes	86	86	86
2	No	14	14	100
	Total	100	100	

Chart 4 Satisfaction Level of Online Shopping

Interpretation

The above chart shows that the analysis of the satisfaction level of online shopping. 86% of candidates satisfy the online shopping and remaining candidates are not satisfaction. It can be concluded that maximum customers are satisfied.

Hypothesis

Ho = There is no relationship between age and income.

Ha = There is a relationship between age and income.

	Age	Income
Mean	25	25
Variance	412	142.6667
Observations	4	4
Df	3	3
F	2.88785	
P(F<=f) one-tail	0.203491	
F Critical one-tail	9.276628	

Hypothesis

There is no significance between the age of the respondents and monthly income. The researcher shows that the applying f- test in the age of the respondents and monthly income. The table value is less than the calculated value. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. That is the table value is 0.2034 but the calculated value is 2.8878.

Findings

- Among the total respondents of the study, the majority of the respondents (50 percentage) have 20-30 age group.
- Majority of the respondents are male (56 percentage) who are married (36 percentage).
- Majority of the respondents (40 percentage) have monthly income less than Rs 10000.
- To analyze the consumer's behavior towards online shopping (86 percentage) satisfied.
- Based on the study, the majority of the respondents (38 percentage) the reason for online shopping for price.
- Majority of the respondents (44 percentage) are influenced to purchase products and services online as per the online advertisement.

Suggestions

- Majority of respondents are the opinion about online shopping is connected in rural areas.
- Majority of the users among higher income groups shops online only. But in Dharmapuri district, middle income and low-income groups are very high. So the online marketers can concentrate on innovative ideas to increase online business through the middle and low-income group. This will be possible only through the price fixation of the product based on this group.
- Website quality creates a positive impact on online shopping satisfaction. So the vendor companies should concentrate more on the quality part of the websites.
- The online vendor should take necessary steps before dispatching the products to the consumer site. It creates the good opinion about the online vendor and creates repurchasing power of the respondents.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Internet shopping is very much similar to conventional non-store shopping. It is just a new method of non-store shopping. This research study has helped in understanding how many people are buying products and services through online shopping. Online shopping is a vast

growing of modern technology. If it is properly utilized with assured safety and security for the transactions, it will be highly competitive and dynamic environment. Internet shoppers have found unique products on the Internet. This use of technology has opened new doors and opportunities that enable for a more convenient lifestyle today. Customer Service and Convenience tend to be three significant dimensions as to why customers prefer internet shopping. Online shopping is a different experience and one can make the shopping creative over the internet as one gets used to it.

References

Books

Berman & Evans, Retail Management, Pearson Education.

Kothari, C. R., (2010). Research Methodology Methods and Techniques, 2nd Revised Edition, New Age International (P) Ltd. Publishers.

Tripathi, P. C., (2007). Research Methodology in Social Sciences, 6th Revised and Enlarged Edition, Sultan Chand & Sons.

Websites

www.google.com

www.wikipedia.com

Web Sources

<http://allsoftsolutions.in/portfolio-filter/our-student-work/>

<http://www.freestudentprojects.com/studentprojectreport/project-srs/online-mobile-shop-project-report/>

<http://www.internationaljournalsrg.org/IJEMS/2017/Volume4-Issue5/IJEMS-V4I5P108.pdf>

http://www.journalrepository.org/media/journals/BJEMT_20/2015/Jul/Putro912015BJEMT18704.pdf

https://cwsglobal.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Final-CfM_Programme_Booklet_Edited_Final.pdf

<https://www.coursehero.com/file/p6gllqd/Factor-4-Effortless-Shopping-This-factor-includes-two-items-as-in-hassle-free/>

<https://www.ijcsmc.com/docs/papers/July2014/V3I7201499a46.pdf>

<https://www.ukessays.com/essays/marketing/a-case-study-of-online-shopping-behavior-marketing-essay.php>

<https://www.wisegeek.com/what-is-online-shopping.htm>